

**OPTIMIZING THE TREATMENT OF DRUG-RESISTANT
PULMONARY TB**

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Annotation: Under the conditions of the tuberculosis epidemic that has developed in recent years, the course of tuberculosis infection and the structure of clinical forms have changed dramatically. Cases of a progressive course of this disease with an acute onset or an acute outbreak of the disease with massive bacterial excretion have become more frequent. The number of patients with primary drug resistance of mycobacterium tuberculosis increased sharply - from 18 to 37%. Modern pathomorphosis of tuberculosis led to a significant decrease in the effectiveness of chemotherapy. On average for In Uzbekistan, only 44.6% of newly diagnosed patients with a treatment period of 8-10 months. are discharged from the hospital with significant improvement (without decay in the lungs and bacterial excretion), at the same time, the effectiveness of conservative treatment of patients with drug-resistant tuberculosis varies from 8 to 29%.

Key words : tuberculosis, drug resistance, treatment effectiveness

The development of resistance in microorganisms to the drugs used to combat them is one of the manifestations of the fundamental biological property of all living organisms - adaptability to changes in environmental conditions [Rudoy N.M., 1964, Slepukha I.M. 1985; Borisov S.E., Sokolova G.B., 2001].

The term "drug resistance" was introduced by Ehrlich at the beginning of the last century, who described this phenomenon in relation to salvarsano -resistant spirochetes in the treatment of patients with syphilis. However, this problem acquired practical significance later - during the period of discovery and widespread use of sulfanilamide

preparations. To quote R. Schnitzer and E. Grunberg : "The history of chemotherapy is also the history of drug resistance in microorganisms." Waksman's discovery of streptomycin in 1943 marked the beginning of a new era of effective tuberculosis control, but the first reports of acquired resistance to this drug appeared as early as 1948 [Crofton J., Mitchinson DA, 1948]. In the 1940s para-aminosalicylic acid [Lexmann , 1943] and thiacetazone [G. Domagk et al ., 1946]. In 1952, isoniazid was created - simultaneously in the USA [W. G Benson et al ., J. Bernstein et al .] and in Germany [G. Domagk et al .]; in the same year, pyrazinamide [S. Kushn et al ., M. Solotorovsky et al .] and cycloserine [Kurosawa , J: Shoji]. In 1956, Ethionamide was discovered [D. Libermann et al ., France], in 1957 - kanamycin [N. Umezawa et al ., Japan].

The introduction into practice of highly effective drugs - isoniazid and its derivatives - also led to the emergence of cases of MBT resistance to drugs of this group [Rudoy N.M., 1969]. Finally, rifampicin appeared in the 1960s [Opopolzer , 1957; France] and ethambutol [J. Thomas et al ., 1961; USA], which made it possible to temporarily overcome the problem of drug resistance [Rist N., Grumbach F., Libermann D., 1959; Wilkinson RG, Shepherd RG, Thomas JP, Booughn C, 1961]. In 1959, capreomycin was isolated [J. Herr et al ., France], which found application in phthisiology several decades later. In the late 80s of the XX century, antibiotics of the fluoroquinolone group were synthesized , some of which are active against MBT [Yew WW et al ., 1994; Mitchinson DA, 1995]. From this period to the present, there are still no new effective anti-TB drugs introduced into clinical practice, while the problem of drug resistance is gaining momentum.

According to the WHO classification (1998), drug-resistant MBT are divided into:

1. monoresistant - to one anti-TB drug
2. polyresistant - to 2 or more anti-TB drugs, but not to the combination of isoniazad and rifampicin
3. multi-drug resistant (at least to the combination of isoniazid and rifampicin)

The introduction of the term MDR by WHO specialists is of practical importance, because at the same time, resistance to the most active against MBT anti-TB drugs (isoniazid and rifampicin) is highlighted.

Of particular practical importance for the clinic is the classification of V.Yu. Mishina and V.I. Chukanova (2002), in which the division of MBT into groups is determined taking into account resistance to a combination of drugs of the 1st and 2nd series:

Group 1 - monoresistant to one main chemopreparates.

2nd group - polyresistant to the main chemopreparates.

Group 3 - polyresistant to a combination of basic and individual reserve drugs.

Group 4 - polyresistant to all main and reserve drugs. It should be noted that at the present time there is not only an increase in the number of patients with LUT, there is a change in the structure of the drug resistance itself, if at the beginning of the history of the use of anti-TB drugs, MBT monoresistance to anti-TB drugs was most common, then at the present stage there is a significant increase in the number of patients with multidrug-resistant and multi -drug resistant pulmonary tuberculosis, which is directly related to the long-term use of basic and reserve drugs, and the lack of new effective anti-TB drugs.

It is also important to distinguish between primary and secondary LU MBT. Primary drug resistance is detected in newly diagnosed tuberculosis patients who have not previously taken anti-TB drugs, it is understood that the patient was infected with initially resistant MBT [Dorozhkova IR, Medvedeva IM, 1997; Borisov S.E., Sokolova G.B., 2001, etc.]. Secondary (acquired) drug resistance is observed in patients with initially sensitive MBT, who develop resistant MBT during inadequate chemotherapy (more than 1 month) [Khomenko A.G., Chukanov V.I. , 1996; Van Rie A., et al ., 1999, Mishin V. Yu , 2001 and others].

In the study of the resection material, the so-called latent drug resistance was described, when resistance to a greater number of chemopreparates is determined in

the cavity than in sputum [Tereshin BC, 1994, Garifullin Z.R., 2001, Strelis A.K. et al ., 2002].

The phenomenon of drug resistance reflects inadequate chemotherapy of tuberculosis [Mishin V. Yu , 2001; Vasiliev. I.A., 2002; Grishin M.N. et al ., 2002; Iseman MD, 1999; Raviglione M :S , 2001.]. At the same time, the most common clinical errors are: short courses of chemotherapy, lack of control over the intake of anti-TB drugs, prescription of less than 4 anti-drug drugs in the intensive phase of chemotherapy, introduction of one new drug in case of failure of the previous treatment regimen, short courses of chemotherapy, lack of control over the intake of anti-TB drugs [Kalandadze Z .F., 1962; Mishin V.Yu., Chukanov V.I., Vasilyeva I.A., 2000; Korablev V.N. et al . 2001]. Previous ineffective treatment is the main risk factor for the development of MDR [Valiev R.Sh., 2000; Vasilyeva I.A., 2002; Kopylova I.F. et al ., 2000; Nechaeva O.B., Skachkova E.I., 2003; Ait Khaled N., Enarson D., Billo N., 1997.].

Since drug treatment of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis is ineffective, many literature sources point to surgical treatment as the only alternative [Perelman M.I., 2001; Doroshenkova A.E., 2003; Erimbetov K.D., 2003; Krivonos P.S., 2003; Nakajima Y., 1997 and others]. The insufficient effectiveness of polychemotherapy should serve as a natural basis for an earlier (after 2 months of treatment) referral of patients for surgical treatment [Perelman MI, 1998; Khomenko A.G., Mishin V.Yu., Chukanov V.I., 1999 and others].

Resume . Analysis of the literature shows a high prevalence of MDR-TB. The leading causes of the current epidemiologically dangerous situation are inadequate chemotherapy, late diagnosis of MBT drug resistance, and the lack of timely surgical treatment. Increasing the effectiveness of treatment of patients with multidrug-resistant tuberculosis is one of the problems of modern phthisiology.

In the publications of domestic and foreign authors concerning the surgical treatment of patients with MDR tuberculosis, in most cases they are talking about pneumonectomy , lobectomy or collapse surgery . Of particular interest from the point

of view of studying the effectiveness of treatment is the little studied group of partial lung resections.

The lack of a unified approach to determining the indications and timing of operations for MDR tuberculosis dictates the need for their development. Given the high risk of postoperative complications, the possibility of recurrence of tuberculosis in patients with multidrug resistance of MBT, there is a need to identify true drug resistance from the surgical material and timely correction of chemotherapy in the immediate postoperative period. There is also a need to determine the duration and nature of postoperative therapy in this category of patients.

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